

Potability Assessment of Borehole Water in Ikate, Lekki-Ajah, Lagos State: Implications for Sustainable Water-Energy Nexus Solutions

Author: Adegbemi Samsondeen Adeyinka

Abstract

Safe drinking water remains a major public health concern, particularly in developing countries where millions of people fall sick annually due to contaminated water sources. This study assessed the potability of borehole water in Ikate-Elegushi, Lekki-Ajah, Lagos State, Nigeria. Five borehole water samples were collected from different residential locations and analyzed for physicochemical, chemical, and microbiological parameters in accordance with the World Health Organization (WHO) and Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ) guidelines. Results revealed that while pH and temperature were within acceptable limits, high concentrations of total dissolved solids, conductivity, salinity, calcium hardness, and bacterial counts exceeded permissible limits. The findings indicate that most borehole water in the study area is unsafe for direct consumption. The study highlights the urgent need for improved water treatment infrastructure, public health awareness, and integration of decentralized renewable energy-powered water treatment systems to address water safety challenges and reduce the energy burden of water purification in underserved communities.

Keywords: Water quality, Borehole water, Potability, Lagos, Water-energy nexus, Renewable energy

1. Introduction

Access to clean and safe drinking water is fundamental to public health and socio-economic development. Despite Nigeria's abundant water resources, only 19% of the population has access to safe drinking water, with access being more limited in low-income and peri-urban communities. Lagos, Nigeria's commercial hub, faces severe water quality challenges due to rapid population growth, urbanization, and environmental pollution. In Ikate-Elegushi, a fast-developing coastal area of Lekki-Ajah, residents rely heavily on borehole water, which is susceptible to contamination from saline intrusion, iron deposits, and anthropogenic pollution.

This study investigates the quality of borehole water in Ikate-Elegushi to determine its suitability for human consumption. The work also discusses the potential of renewable energy-powered treatment systems as sustainable solutions for improving potable water access in similar resource-constrained settings.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

Ikate-Elegushi is a residential community located along the Lekki–Epe Expressway in Eti-Osa Local Government Area, Lagos State, Nigeria. It lies near the Atlantic Ocean, Lagos Lagoon, and Lekki Lagoon, which increases its groundwater’s vulnerability to salinity and contamination.

TABLE 2.1: BOREHOLE LOCATIONS AND THEIR RESPECTIVE SAMPLE NUMBER.

S/N	SAMPLE CODE	LOCATION OF SAMPLE	STREET NAME	LONGITUDE AND LATITUDE
1	Sample A	Mr.Godwin’s Residence	Admiral Gabriel Okoi Street	6.432195 (6 ⁰ 25’55.9”N) 3.481757 (3 ⁰ 28’54.3”E)
2	Sample M	Legacy place	Ikate Bus Stop	6.435964 (6 ⁰ 26’09.5”N) 3.487825 (3 ⁰ 29’16.2”E)
3	Sample P	Ola Ade Residence	Kusenla Road	6.438367 (6 ⁰ 26’18.1”N) 3.490705 (3 ⁰ 29’26.5”E)
4	Sample K	Elegushi Palace	Oba Yekinni Elegushi Road	6.435766 (6 ⁰ 26’08.8”N) 3.486435 (3 ⁰ 29’11.2”E)
5	Sample F	Chief Opemolua Residence	Oba Yekinni Elegushi Road	6.438955 (6 ⁰ 26’20.2”N) 3.487330 (3 ⁰ 29’14.4”E)

2.2 Sampling and Laboratory Analysis

Five borehole water samples were collected from different locations (Mr. Godwin’s Residence, Legacy Place, Ola Ade Residence, Elegushi Palace, and Chief Opemolua Residence). Standard sampling procedures were followed, and samples were transported to the Civil and Environmental Engineering Laboratory, University of Lagos. Samples were analyzed for physicochemical parameters (temperature, pH, turbidity, conductivity, total dissolved solids, total hardness, salinity), chemical parameters (chloride, sulphate, nitrate, phosphate, iron, copper, manganese, zinc, calcium hardness), and microbiological

parameters (total bacterial counts, fecal coliforms) using WHO and NSDWQ standards as benchmarks.

Fig 2.2: Water samples from different location within Ikate community

3. Results

3.1 Physicochemical Parameters

- pH values ranged from 7.04–7.60 (within WHO limits of 6.5–8.5)
- TDS ranged from 387–2390 ppm; samples A, F, K, and M exceeded the 500 ppm limit
- Conductivity ranged from 570–3170 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$; four samples exceeded the 1200 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ limit
- Salinity ranged from 280–1630 ppm; two samples exceeded the 1000 ppm limit

Table 3.1: Physical quality of borehole water sample.

PHYSICAL QUALITY OF BOREHOLE SAMPLE						
Parameter	WHO limits	RESULT				
		Sample A	Sample F	Sample K	Sample M	Sample P
Appearance	Clear	Clear	Clear	Clear	Clear	Clear
Colour	Colourless	Light brown	Light brown	Light brown	Light brown	Colourless
Odour	Odourless	Odourless	Odourless	Objectionable	Objectionable	Odourless
Temperature on field °C	Ambient	26.5	27.0	27.0	26.0	27.0
pH@26°C-27°C [no unit]	6.50 – 8.50	7.36	7.50	7.04	7.20	7.60
Turbidity [FTU]	5.0	1.82	1.16	0.96	1.19	2.11
Conductivity [μscm^{-1}]	1200	3170	2120.0	1491.0	1267.0	570.0
Total dissolve solid [ppm]	500	2390	1550.0	1060.0	888.0	387.0
Total solid [ppm]	1500	2392.1	1550.0	1061.3	888.6	388.1
Salinity [ppm]	1000	1630	1070.0	740.0	630.0	280.0

3.2 Chemical Parameters

- Calcium hardness ranged from 98–300 ppm; all samples exceeded the WHO limit of 75 ppm
- Chloride ranged from 92–1570 ppm; several samples exceeded the 250 ppm limit
- Iron ranged from 0.157–0.372 mg/L; one sample slightly exceeded the 0.3 mg/L limit
- Phosphate exceeded the 0.03 mg/L limit in all samples (0.42–1.28 mg/L)

Table 3.2: Chemical quality of borehole water sample

CHEMICAL QUALITY OF BOREHOLE SAMPLE						
Parameters	WHO limits	RESULTS(ppm)				
		Sample A	Sample F	Sample K	Sample M	Sample P
Alkalinity-M (ppm CaCo ³)	500	550	570	504	460	284
Acidity-P (ppm Cac0 ₃)	500	60	40	28	32	20
Total hardness (ppm CaCo ₃)	200	620	510	488	342	240
Calcium Hardness (CaCo ₃)	75	300	210	216	124	98
Chloride, Cl ⁻ (ppm)	250	1570	1060	468	360	92
Sulphate, So ₄ ²⁻ (ppm)	200	122	194	72	89.2	22
Residual Chlorine (ppm)	0.2	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Nitrite, NO ₂ ⁻ (ppm)	0.0	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Nitrate, NO ₃ ⁻ (ppm)	30	4.61	6.92	5.84	6.26	1.15
Ammonia N- NH ₃ , (ppm)	0.5	0.04	ND	ND	0.46	0.00
Arsenic, As (ppm)	0.01	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Phosphate, Po ₄ ³⁻ (ppm)	0.03	1.28	1.16	0.96	1.21	0.42
Iron, Fe ²⁺ (ppm)	0.3	0.296	0.372	0.265	0.226	0.157
Copper, Cu, (ppm)	1.5	0.0714	0.092	0.824	0.0425	0.0271
Manganese, Mn (ppm)	0.5	0.096	0.116	0.04	0.006	0.001
Zinc, Zn, (ppm)	0.3	0.0712	0.052	0.082	0.072	0.042
Lead, Pb, (ppm)	0.01	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Cadmium, Cd (ppm)	0.01	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	---	6.2	7.40	5.21	7.2	6.1

3.3 Microbiological Parameters

- Total bacterial counts ranged from 120–210 cfu/ml, exceeding the 100 cfu/ml permissible limit
- No fecal coliforms were detected

Table 3.3: Microbiological quality of borehole water sample

MICROBIOLOGICAL QUALITY OF BOREHOLE WATER SAMPLE						
Organisms	WHO/NSD WQ limits	RESULTS [Count (cfu/ml)]				
		Sample A	Sample F	Sample K	Sample M	Sample P
Faecal Coliform	Nil	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Clostridium perfringens	Nil	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Total bacteria counts	100	180	180	210	140	120
Staphylococcus aureus	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.0	0.0
Salmonella	Nil	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Shigella	Nil	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Yeast/mould	10.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	0.0	0.0

4. Discussion

The results show that most borehole water samples from Ikate-Elegushi fail to meet WHO and NSDWQ standards due to high TDS, conductivity, salinity, hardness, and bacterial contamination. High salinity and hardness can cause infrastructure corrosion and pose health risks, while bacterial contamination indicates inadequate protection from surface pollution sources.

Water-Energy Nexus Implications: Treating such contaminated water requires significant energy input for disinfection, filtration, and desalination. In Lagos, where grid power is unreliable, the use of decentralized solar-powered treatment systems (e.g., solar-driven reverse osmosis, UV disinfection, or chlorination) can improve water safety while reducing reliance on diesel-powered systems. Integrating renewable energy into small-

scale water treatment offers a sustainable pathway for improving water access in underserved areas like Ikate-Elegushi.

5. Conclusion

This study revealed that borehole water in Ikate-Elegushi is largely non-potable and poses potential public health risks. There is an urgent need for water quality monitoring, community awareness campaigns, and investment in treatment infrastructure. Embedding renewable energy technologies in decentralized water treatment systems could help ensure safe drinking water while addressing the energy challenges associated with water purification in Nigeria.

6. References

- Adekunle LV, Sridhar MKC, Ajayi AA, Oluwade PA, Olawuyi JF (2004). Assessment of the health and socio-economic implication of sachet water in Ibadan, Nigeria. *Afr. J. Biomed. Res.* 7(1):5-8.
- Shittu OB, Olaitan JO, Amusa TS (2008). Physio-Chemical and Bacteriological Analysis of Water Used for Drinking and Swimming Purpose. *Afr. J. Biochem. Res.* 11:285-290.
- WHO (2006). *Guidelines for Drinking-water Quality*. 3rd edition.
- Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ), SON (2018)
- Groundwater Foundation (2019). Groundwater contamination. Retrieved from <https://www.groundwater.org/get-informed/groundwater/contamination.html>
- Postigo, C. et al. (2018). Groundwater pollution. *ScienceDirect Topics*.
- Sheridan Haack (2017). Bacteria and their effects on ground-water quality. USGS.
- Akoteyon, I. (2013). Characterization of groundwater hydrochemistry and quality assessment in Eti-Osa, Lagos-Nigeria. *Ethiopian Journal of Environmental Studies and Management* 6(3).